

Assessment of Natural Springs across Different Agro-Ecologies of Balochistan, Pakistan, for Sustainable Management

Arshad Ashraf^{1*}, Naveed Mustafa¹, Imran Ahmad¹, Bilal Iqbal¹

¹ Climate, Energy and Water Research Institute, National Agricultural Research Centre (NARC), Islamabad, Pakistan

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Author info:

Corresponding Author.

Arshad Ashraf

mashr22@yahoo.com

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ABSTRACT

Rapid growth in urban developments and climate change has put high pressure on the existing water resources in the arid region of South Asia. It is necessary to identify effective water management and adaptation strategies to minimize risks of a changing environment. The current study focuses on examining the potential of spring resource and significant factors in various ecologies of Balochistan, Pakistan. The findings of the study revealed a total of 10180 springs in the province, which exist in variable concentrations in different physiographic and rainfall regimes. The majority of springs, about 39.1%, were identified in the low mountains, 28.6% in the middle mountains, and 22.3% in the Siwaliks. The density was found to be high, i.e., about 0.11 springs/km² in the middle mountains, 0.08 springs/km² in the high mountains, and 0.04 springs/km² in the low mountains. The spring density was observed to be high, i.e., about 0.06 springs/km², in the >400 mm and 200-300 mm rainfall regimes, while it was noticed to be least, i.e., about 0.01 springs/km², in the <100 mm regime. The diversity in climate and physiography observed in different ecologies demands site-specific resource management and adaptations to climate change. An integrated water management approach adopting a suitable set of available technologies (rainwater harvesting, high-efficiency irrigation systems, and surface storage) could be beneficial to sustain agriculture in different water-stressed ecologies of the province.

Introduction.

The rapid urbanization and changes in climate and land use are placing a great deal of strain on the natural resources and agriculture, especially in the large arid region of Pakistan (Baocheng et al. 2024). Due to increased urbanization, increased agricultural activity, and frequent drought conditions in the Indus basin (Miyan, 2015), groundwater use has increased many times (Qureshi, 2011; Laghari et al., 2012; Nasir et al., 2018; Sadaf et al., 2019). The effects of climate change on agro-climate systems have led to increased water stress in arid agricultural zones (Aliyari et al., 2021). The population of Balochistan increased from about 6.6 million in 1998 to 14.9 million in 2023, according to the recent census (<https://www.pbs.gov.pk/>). Springs are lifelines for Balochistan's people, agriculture, and environment. Many rural and semi-urban communities depend on springs for their daily drinking water needs. In remote areas where piped water is unavailable, springs remain the primary source of clean water. Springs feed traditional irrigation systems like *karez* (underground channels) and open canals, enabling farming in arid regions. They support the cultivation of crops such as apples, grapes, almonds, and wheat, which are crucial for local livelihood (Akhtar et al. 2021). Balochistan's pastoral communities rely on springs to water their herds of sheep, goats, and camels. Springs sustain local biodiversity, including vegetation, wildlife, and aquatic species. Springs often create localized microclimates and provide essential water for vegetation, supporting unique biodiversity in otherwise arid landscapes. They can form small oases that are vital for local flora and fauna and cultural and historical significance.

Spring management and conservation have received relatively little attention despite their critical importance. There are significant information gaps in the scant, dispersed, and spatially irregular literature that is currently available on spring ecological integrity (Cantonati et al. 2020). Agro-ecological maps displayed regions with consistent physiography, land use, climate, and soil/landform characteristics. The worsening state of some of the springs due to the increasing impact of anthropogenic factors must be addressed on time to avert future spring contamination in the area. For the majority of geographical locations and the few of regional significance, the exact number of springs is unknown. Reliable information and assessment of existing resources are necessary for future planning and development of the arid areas (Chaudhry and Rasul, 2004). The fundamental geographic data of springs is necessary for effective management of the spring ecosystems by water management and conservation organizations (Gupta and Kulkarni 2017). The situation of water scarcity can be addressed through proper management of springs in different ecologies. In order to improve agricultural productivity and economic growth in various agro-ecologies, it is necessary to identify resource potential and strategies.

The present study focuses on investigating spring resource potential and influential factors in different ecologies of Balochistan, Pakistan, to identify efficient water management and adaptation strategies. The agro-ecologies of the province were reclassified to account for major changes that occurred in the environment during the last several decades in the region. The study would support future planning and management of agriculture and water resources for economic uplift of the province in the future.

Geophysical setup

The Balochistan, in the country's southwest, is the largest province by area, spanning some 347,190 km². The province has a predominantly warm desertic hyper-arid to semi-arid subtropical climate, having scanty precipitation with a high temporal and spatial variability. The upper highlands have warm summers and very cold winters, while the lower coastal areas endure hot, dry summers and winters that range from extreme cold to mild. The rainfall over 400 mm is dominant in the north, which gradually reduces to nearly 50 mm towards the south (Ashraf and Majeed 2006). The province experiences highest rainfall season from December to March due to the western disturbance system,

while the remaining months (April to November) receive relatively little rainfall (Ashraf et al. 2022). The soils are mostly shallow, unstable, and heterogeneous over mountainous terrain, and moderately deep, calcareous, gravelly and medium-textured in the valleys. Most of the province relies on two farming methods: sailaba (using floodwater) and khushkaba (using rainfall and runoff).

Groundwater is generally accessed through Karezes, tubewells, and open dugwells for irrigation and domestic purposes (Ashraf and Majeed 2006). More than 80% of farmers in the province are small landholders with less than two hectares of land. Major crops grown in the province include wheat, rice, sorghum, barley, maize, oilseeds, and a variety of vegetables and fruits. At places the crops are grown using streams, springs, or “Karezes” water wherever available. The parts of Kachhi plains in the east are irrigated through canal water, where rice is grown in the kharif season. The environment of the province favors the cultivation of many fresh and dry fruits, such as apples, apricots, grapes, pomegranates, cherries, plums, olives, dates, and almonds. Karezes and springs have historically been essential to the growth of the horticultural sector in the Balochistan province. The spring water is redirected to small fields for crop cultivation and orchard raising in the highlands. The springs are essential watering locations for cattle, sheep, goats, and camels in arid and semi-arid grazing areas where alternative water sources are limited.

Spring sources in Balochistan

Many springs in Balochistan are primarily formed due to geological fractures (faults and cracks in mountains) allowing groundwater to surface; karst aquifers (limestone/dolomite rocks) that store and release water naturally; and precipitation (rain and snow) seeping into the ground and emerging at lower elevations. They originate from groundwater stored in fractured hard rock formations, particularly limestones (like the Chiltan, Parh, and Kirthar formations) and sandstones (Siwalik Group). These rocks, when fractured by tectonic activity (such as the Chaman Fault, which influences groundwater flow in areas like Chaman and Nushki), can create pathways for water to accumulate and emerge at the surface. At places, springs emerge along fault lines where groundwater flow is intercepted or forced to the surface due to changes in rock permeability or structural discontinuities. The famous group of springs called Moola Chotok near Khuzdar is located at the junction of two mountains that have been eroded by water for many years. Hot springs, such as those in Mangi Dam and Ziarat, result from geothermal activity that occurred in the subsurface geology. At places valley springs emerge in lowlands, often from alluvial aquifers. There exist some thermal springs in the province also, which are a potential source for geothermal energy. These are typically associated with deep-seated geological structures like faults that allow hot water from the earth's interior to rise to the surface. Many streams in Balochistan are ephemeral (non-perennial), carrying water only after rainfall floods that infiltrate the alluvial fans and piedmont plains, contributing to groundwater recharge and subsequently feeding springs and karezes. The recharge by precipitation, the springsheds size, and the pressure of aquifer water regulate the discharge of the springs (USGS 2019).

2. Data and Methodology

The thematic data on topography, climate (1989–2019), hydrology, irrigation systems, soils, and crops were collected from various source institutions, such as Survey of Pakistan (SoP), Pakistan Meteorological Department (PMD), and the provincial agriculture departments. The spring data was acquired from SoP, which included locations and geographic coordinates collected through Global Positioning System (GPS) surveys. The discharge data of springs was not available, likely due to geographic and technical constraints, except for limited data on Karez systems reported in some previous studies (e.g., Halcrow 1987; Ashraf and Majeed 2006). The Copernicus Global Land Cover product (100 m resolution) of the year 2020 was downloaded to examine land use/land cover (LULC) in the province. For topographic and relief analysis, the Shuttle Radar Topography Mission SRTM-

DEM 90 m data was obtained from the NASA website (www.jpl.nasa.gov/). The eight-day seamless NDVI (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index) product of 250 m of the 2020 period was downloaded from the site <https://modis.gsfc.nasa.gov/data/> for relationship analysis with the spring distribution. The product is created from Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) surface reflectance data and is important for assessing vegetation status, such as differentiating between vegetated and non-vegetated areas (Huang et al. 2021). The NDVI index is the ratio of highly reflective near-infrared (NIR) wavelengths to highly absorptive red wavelengths as given in Equation 1.

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR - Red}{NIR + Red} \quad (1)$$

NDVI classification was performed following Lourenço and Landim (2004) to define five distinct classes, i.e., NDVI values are categorized to represent varying vegetation conditions: values below 0 indicate bare soil or water, 0–0.2 signify very low density, 0.2–0.4 represent low density, 0.4–0.6 denote moderate density, and values exceeding 0.6 correspond to high vegetation density (Table 1). The base layers of different thematic data were developed in a geographic information system (GIS) using the Transverse Mercator coordinate system for integration and overlay analysis. The physiographic zones were generated through classification of the DEM data (Hubert, 1995, and others), which include high mountains (>3000 m elevation), middle mountains (2000–3000 m), low mountains (1200–2000 m), Siwaliks (700–1200 m), hilly areas or plateaus (300–700 m), and lowlands (<300 m elevation) (Figure 1). The agro-ecological zones were delineated based on landforms, physiography, land use, and agro-climate data through overlay analysis of different thematic layers in ArcGIS software.

Figure 1. Extent of various physiographic regions in the province

Table 1. NDVI classes used for spring distribution analysis.

S.No.	NDVI	Cover condition
1	≤ 0	Soil/water
2	0–0.2	Low vegetation
3	0.2–0.4	Sparse vegetation
4	0.4–0.6	Transition vegetation
5	>0.6	Dense vegetation

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Spatial analysis of springs

Balochistan is home to over 10180 natural springs that play a crucial role in sustaining local communities and ecosystems (Figure 2). More than fifty percent of springs exist in the four districts only, i.e., Khuzdar, Pashin, Qilla Saifullah, and Qilla Abdullah. Maximum springs were observed in Khuzdar and minimum in the Nasirabad district. Some of the known springs in the province are listed in Table 2. Major physiographic regions observed in the province include low mountains over 26.6% of the area, middle mountains over 7.1% of the area, and Siwaliks over 28.5% of the area of the province (Table 3 and Figure 1). The springs exist in variable numbers in different physiographic regions. For example, a majority of about 39.1% of springs were identified in the low mountains, 28.6% of springs in the middle mountains, and 22.3% of springs in the Siwaliks (Table 3). The density was found to be high, i.e., about 0.11 springs/km² in the middle mountains, 0.08 springs/km² in the high mountains, and 0.04 springs/km² in the low mountains. Here precipitation at higher elevations may favor recharging of the subsurface aquifers. The less than 0.02 springs/km² densities were noted in the lowlands and hilly areas, likely due to high aridity conditions. Overall the density was observed to be over 0.03 springs/km² in the province.

Table 2. The locally named springs in different districts of Balochistan province.

Awaran	Chat Kan	Bekan	Ghar Nishpa China	Sasankai	Maiiau Kar China
Jungo Chakul	Jaki Spring	Bhuga	Ghor Madai China	Shin Zhawari	Malau China
Rahat Chakul	Kul Kan spring	Chahgai	Khwadzai China	Shaikhan China	Mankai Chian
Bolan	Matabi Spring	Changai Obo	Shobbar Spring	Sharaonah	Mazhbazi Maghzal
Garmab Spring	Murad	Chegai China	Sinkai Samuz	Shela Gat	Rano Tizha

Gorandani	Nitage	Chinar	Sinzali Gat	Shenkai Tasah	Shin Nishpa China
Gura	Piaram Spring	Chinjan Tsahan	Sir Karez	Sorai	Taghha China
Halap na Dir	Samiza	Chuwo China	Spera Tangi Tsah	Spangwar Khezai	Taude Oba
Pab na Dun	Shakar gai Ab	Dabrai Tsah	Sperowun	Sra Lara	Sibi
Sanganj	Sur Spring	Dadan	Spin Jamaat Tsah	Takai Khezai	Dirghi spring
Chagai	Khuzdar	Dargai Obo	Spina	Tarki	Washuk
Dal	Arghi Chakul	Darra	Spine Obo	Tarwaki Gat	Khairaduni
Shamzai Ap Dir	Bakhtu na Dir	Dehsal Tash	Sra Tsohi	Tlerai Tsah	Musafir Chakul
Zank	Banda Ku	Dhram	Sre Sharanai Zawarai	Tor Pazhai	Zhob
Harnai	Baror Chakul	Durgai Oba	Stawai Obo	Tsargai	Ali Tangi China
Angur China	Baror Lak	Gagarai	Stawai Tsah	Usperia China	Ambar Zamkai China
Channu Kan	Bhagu	Gatai Tangai Tsahan	Suhoi	Zangal	Dargai China
Darbali China	Chakul	Ghaz China	Sur Samuzai	Zindai Obe	Datwala China
Ghalrug	Chakuri	Ghurrun Tsah China	Sur Tangai Tsah	Zindai Punga Obo China	Dwe Shakhei Tsah
Kahri Kan	Chham	Girdai China	Surkai	Mastung	Gandherai Tsah
Khandki Kanrh	Chutok	Guki Obo	Surkai Chamozgai	Bibi Chakat	Graang China
Kuchsa China	Dhaniar	Hadire Tsah	Tar Tangi	Rushkhar	Haidara China
Malana China	Gauharo	Halal China	Tarakai Khezai Tsahan	Tat Chakat	Inzargai China

Matzar	Get Toba	Ishan	Targai	Toba	Kacram China
Nasir Chaman	Ghuno	Jangi Khezai Tsah	Tarkai Tangai Obo	Musakhel	Kamar China
Shape Kan	Gohramji	Kabirai	Tierai Tsahan	Mazar Lunah China	Karai China
Sinzala Kan	Habbu	Kabul	Tirkha Oba	Saz Band China	Khoza Changai China
Tamraz China	Haiar Dir	Kach	Tirkhe Gare Tsah	Tar Tongai China	Laka China
Tarkh China	Hanjrari	Kama Sinazai Obo	Torkhezhe Tsah	Zharai Uba	Laswandai China
Tarwakai China	Hesharki	Kandao Oba	Trai Tsahan	Panjgur	Makrani China
Tarwr kan	Jabali	Khashankai Tsahan	Tsahan	Chakil	Manzghalia China
Tirwakai China	Joi	Khat Khezai	Tsalarai Tsahan	Gawad Band	Mitran Takrai Tusa
Tisi	Jukar	Khaza	Tsale Tsohi Obo	Gawaran Kalgi	Moshkanai China
Tsapparai China	Kage	Khazana Tsah	Tsohi	Genrase	Mullakhai China
Wazi China	Karbana na Kumbh	Khosai China	Turkhuk	Jannat	Nakhai Tatal
Zirgai China	Kashi	Khozai Tsah	Urmazh Oba	Lai	Obour Zinky China
Kalat	Khand Chakul	Khozobai Tsah	Wazai	Meshgud Sor	Orista China
Adina	Khati	Khulgai Oba	Wcuskai Tsahan	Strangar	Pareza Chiina
Auahdad na Dr	Khondi	Khusan Obo	Wulg	Tanag	Sambarai China
Azmat	Kumar	Khushankai China	Wulgai China	Woshap	Samuzai China
Balwan	Kumb	Khut Kandai	Zahib China	Zawari	Sarwat China

Bhalla Shishari	Kumbhi	Khwazhagai Obo	Zangmurgh Tsah	Pishin	Sasandai China
Bhatti	Lakha na Chakul	Korai Tsah	Zar Aghargai China	Aghbargai	Shabangar Toshai
Bhaurteel	Langari	Multana Spring	Zhiarai Khezhai Tsahan	Akhtu	Shinkoi Manda China
Boji	Machi	Murghakai Tsah	Zhira Tsah	Amrat Chashma	Skarai China
Borvi	Magudo	Naghargai Obo	Ziaba Tsah	Babul China	Spinkai China
Burbur	Makri	Nakshe	Zobosar Obo	Beiguna	Sra Kamrai China
Burhus Talari	Mohan Kumbh	Narai Toi Tsahan	Zuba China	Gawah Khezai	Stawai China
Chakul Umraha	Nali	Narai Tor China	Kohlu	Katwai China	Surangat China
Chashmah	Paghuti	Nasir Wai	Shahin Tobai China	Khwaja Gul Chashma	Surkai pail China
Dranjan	Pashtagi	Natuh China	Lasbela	Klak	Tanga China
Gem	Pir Dam	Nek Bakhtaorr	Chakuli	Muhammand Shah	Tangi China
Geti	Pugthi	Parshai Obo	Hanjiri	Obashtai	Tarkhu China
Gndap	Reg Khanber	Pasti Oba	Loralai	Sarkai	Tazai China
Gudai	Sari	Peshai China	Adagai China	Ser Haba Tarai	Torkanrai China
Hanari	Shahni	Pinza Tilare Tsah	Angi	Shina khawara	Zhwandai Oba
Hanaruriki	Shum Sham	Plan khwar Tsah	Bashal Tsah	Shrara Khezai	Ziarat
Hapural	Shutkal	Poro Tsah	Bedar Gat	Smazai	Aspin Khetrai
Ispekhi Dun	Sor Dir Kandol	Sadwale Tsahan	Chirgan China	Speral Gad	Chakhan

Jatuna Dir	Soro	Saimuz Kar Obo	Gider Tsah	Spin Karez	Dagarai
Karia	Soruk	Samzgai Tsah	Gidwan Taswai	Spin Khazai	Ghunza
Karohli	Pirae Chakul	Sang Sahan	Jilga	Tangai	Jani China
Khel Chakul	Siahmosh Chakul	Sarai China	Kanrekai China	Tor Shakh	Kashai
Khui	Tafu Pirahi	Sawani	Khani China	Wrazrumba	Kuchalai
Laghamgi	Walidad Khand	Shagai China	Khusan	Zarandukai	Lakai
Mand na Dir Spring	Winar	Shan Tangai	Kudam	Quetta	Mahat Tang
Masiti	Zard Chakul	Shankul Tsah	Mar Tsah	Darai Chakul	Mazai China
Mekh	Killa Abdullah	Sharandai Tsahan	Murghi Tobai	Kaga Dargah	Pui China
Shishari	Zaghumai China	Sheran	Nalu Gat	Loe Skhabal	Sagar
Sikin	Killa Saifullah	Shiany China	Nargasi Tsahan	Milanr	Shaista
Spring Hampada	Adam Tsah	Shin Tankai China	Nigang	Nauda Nargasai	Shambe Aghbarg
Tachhok	Adwal China	Shin Walgoi	Pakha Ubou	Slam Chapi Chakul	Shaukai Khezai
Ushkun	Ara Gare Tash	Shing Pasta	Pakhe Obe	Sherani	Spedar China
Kech	Azak China	Shinkai Khezai Tsah	Push Obo	Bahlol Ziarat China	Tangor
Bajil	Babu Tabai Obo	Shishankai	Qadari Toba China	Chaman Chaina	Tarnao
Charoani Spring	Bagahrul	Shna Lazhge Tsah	Sar Spina	Kut Trweh	Tora Khezai

Figure 2. Spring distribution in different district of Balochistan

Table 3. Summary of spring resource in various physiographic regions

Region	Coverage		Springs		Density (Sp/km ²)
	Km ²	%	Number	%	
High Mount	185	0.1	14	0.1	0.08
Middle Mount	24729	7.1	2806	27.6	0.11
Low Mount	92180	26.6	3978	39.1	0.04
Siwaliks	98808	28.5	2268	22.3	0.02
Hilly area	71488	20.6	866	8.5	0.01
Lowlands	59800	17.2	248	2.4	0.00
Total	347190	100.0	10180	100.0	0.03

3.2 Springs analysis by rainfall

The spring distribution was analyzed under variable rainfall regimes of the province. The 100–200 mm rainfall range indicated maximum coverage of about 43.8%, followed by the 200–300 mm range with coverage of about 24.7% (Table 4 and Figure 3). The greater than 400 mm exhibited the least coverage of about 0.4%, followed by the 300–400 mm range, which covers about 8% of the province area. More than 50% of springs were identified in the 200-300 mm rainfall regime and 28.9% of springs in the 100-200 mm range. The 300-400 mm regime contains 13.3% of springs, while the > 400 mm regime contains 0.8% of springs in the province (Table 4). The spring density was observed to be high, i.e., about 0.06 springs/km², in the >400 mm and 200-300 mm rainfall regimes, while it was noticed to be least, i.e., about 0.01 springs/km², in the <100 mm regime. The arid condition

together with hard rock formations generally hinders groundwater and spring recharge. However, higher rainfall at elevated terrain may contribute recharge to groundwater aquifers at variable depths. The precipitation in the highlands (e.g., Quetta, Pishin, Zhob), along with snowmelt in higher elevations, infiltrates the ground to recharge the aquifers that feed the springs.

Figure 3. Annual rainfall variations in Balochistan province

Table 4. Summary of spring resource in various physiographic regions

Rainfall (mm)	Coverage		Springs		Density (Sp/km ²)
	Km ²	%	Number	%	
<100	80078	23.1	695	6.8	0.01
100–200	151953	43.8	2938	28.9	0.02
200–300	85899	24.7	5113	50.2	0.06
300–400	27823	8.0	1349	13.3	0.05
>400	1437	0.4	85	0.8	0.06
Total	347190	100.0	10180	100.0	0.03

3.3 Springs analysis by NDVI

The spring concentration was assessed under variable classes of NDVI in the province. The 0–0.2 NDVI range (representing low vegetation) exhibited maximum coverage of about 89.4%, followed by the 0.2–0.4 range (representing sparse vegetation) with coverage of about 10.1% (Table 5). In fact, according to FAO (1983), over 93% of the area of Balochistan can be characterized as rangeland that provides grazing opportunities for livestock rearing. The > 0.6 NDVI (dense vegetation) was observed over a 11 km² area only. Major spring concentration, i.e., about 87.6%, was noticed in the 0–0.2 NDVI class, while 12.1% of springs were observed within the 0.2–0.4 NDVI class. There were 32 springs identified in the 0.4–0.6 class (representing transition vegetation) in the study area (Table 5). The spring density was observed to be higher, i.e., 0.04 springs/km², in the 0.2–0.4 class than in

other classes. The higher NDVI represents high wet conditions, likely because of favorable conditions of subsurface moisture in an area (Yun-Hao et al. 2003). According to a study by Ashraf and Ali (2025), spring density exhibited a positive relationship with rainfall and NDVI classes in the Himalayan watershed, suggesting that wet conditions have a beneficial impact on maintaining the spring resource.

Figure 4. NDVI variation in the Balochistan province

Table 5. Summary of spring resource in various NDVI classes

NDVI	Coverage		Springs		Density (Sp/km ²)
	Km ²	%	Number	%	
≤ 0	334	0.1	0	0.0	0.00
0–0.2	310362	89.4	8911	87.6	0.03
0.2–0.4	35282	10.2	1236	12.1	0.04
0.4–0.6	1201	0.3	32	0.3	0.03
>0.6	11	0.0	0	0.0	0.00
Total	347190	100.0	10180	100.0	0.03

3.4 Springs analysis by agro-ecologies

Agro-ecological zones offer pertinent data on the state of the environment today, which is crucial for setting priorities for agricultural and natural resource research (Corbett, 1996; Fischer et al., 2006). The major agro-ecological zones identified in the province include the desert zone (over 22.7%), the dry plateau (over 16%), the northern highlands (over 15.8%), and the coastal zone (over 14.6%) of the province (Table 6). The dry uplands, plains, and Suleiman mountain zones stretch over 12.3%, 11%, and 7.6% of the area, respectively. The dry uplands and dry plateau occupy the central parts, whereas the desert zone is dominant in the northwestern part of the province (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Spring distribution in various agro-ecologies of Balochistan

Table 6. Spring distribution in various agro-ecological regions of Balochistan

Region	Coverage		Springs		Density (Sp/km ²)
	Km ²	%	Number	%	
Northern highlands	54981	15.8	4466	43.9	0.08
Dry uplands	42594	12.3	1744	17.1	0.04
Suleiman mountains	26511	7.6	1127	11	0.04
Plains	38287	11.0	185	1.8	0.00
Desert zone	78644	22.7	515	5.1	0.01
Dry plateau	55547	16.0	1596	15.7	0.03
Coastal zone	50625	14.6	547	5.4	0.01
Total	347190	100.0	10180	100	0.03

The spring concentration was observed to be variable in different ecologies depending on the topography, physiography, hydrogeology, and climate of the region. A maximum of about 44% of springs with a density of about 0.08 springs/km² was observed in the northern highlands ecology (Table 6). About 11% of the springs with a density of about 0.04 springs/km² lie in the Suleiman Mountains zone that falls mainly in the monsoon regime in the northeast side of the province. Similarly, the central uplands zone consists of about 17% of the springs with a density of about 0.04 springs/km². The desert and coastal zones contain 515 and 547 springs, respectively, with densities of about 0.01 springs/km² each. The low densities may be the result of scanty rainfall and consequently insufficient recharge conditions in these ecologies.

The springs are facing a multitude of challenges that threaten their very existence and the livelihoods dependent on them. These challenges are interconnected, stemming from a combination of environmental factors, climate change (reduced rainfall), human activities (overexploitation, contamination from waste, and deforestation), and governance issues. The groundwater extraction has been increased by 94% from 1993 up till 2008 in the province (Ashraf and ul Hasan 2020; Akhtar et al. 2021), which has impacted the groundwater aquifers (Memon et al. 2017). The declining of water tables as a result of overexploitation coupled with recurrent droughts during the last several decades has serious repercussions for the availability of drinking water and irrigation (Khair et al. 2012; Ahmed et al. 2018). Deforestation and rangeland degradation are significant problems in the province that contribute to ecosystem instability and environmental issues (Ahmad et al. 2012; Islam et al. 2013). Moreover, weak governance, lack of effective water management policies, and poor enforcement of environmental laws fail to protect springs from pollution and overuse. Addressing these challenges requires a multi-faceted approach involving strong policy and regulatory frameworks, infrastructure development, community engagement, and climate change adaptation (Ashraf et al. 2016; Karimi et al. 2024).

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Data availability statement: Data will be available on responsible request

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4. Conclusions

The present study focuses on investigating spring resource potential and efficient adaptation strategies in different ecologies of Balochistan, Pakistan. There were seven agro-ecological zones that were reclassified based on agro-climate, physiography, and land use of the province. Balochistan province is rich in 10180 natural springs that exist in variable numbers in different physiographic regions. Majority of about 39.1% springs were identified in the low mountains, 28.6% in the middle mountains, and 22.3% in the Siwaliks. The density was found to be high, i.e., about 0.11 springs/km² in the middle mountains, 0.08 springs/km² in the high mountains, and 0.04 springs/km² in the low mountains. Here precipitation at higher elevations may favor recharging of the subsurface aquifers. The spring density was observed to be high, i.e., about 0.06 springs/km², in the >400 mm and 200-300 mm rainfall regimes, while it was noticed to be least, i.e., about 0.01 springs/km², in the <100 mm regime. Sustainable management is essential to ensure their continued benefits for future generations. In these ecologies, climate-smart agriculture (crops that can withstand heat and drought conditions), high-efficiency irrigation systems (HEIS), and better agro-silvo-pastoral management are essential. Appropriate long-term planning, climate change adaptations, and the removal of institutional barriers to effective water management policies are required for critical areas experiencing water scarcity problems. Following recommendations are suggested to improve spring management and economic development in this region in future:

- There is a need to sustain spring recharge through developing and strengthening recharge facilities (i.e., leaky dams, check structures) and introducing programs of afforestation to improve water retention in the uplands.
- It is necessary to protect the springsheds from overexploitation of groundwater through tubewells, deforestation, and rangeland degradation to sustain spring resource in the province.

- In regions where there is scarce spring water, practices such as water conservation, irrigation efficiency, recycled wastewater use, and crop selection with lower water use should be implemented. Proper storage and distribution systems of spring water can lead to efficient water use for livelihood improvement.
- A repository system can be prepared to record extensive information on the trends of spring discharges, water budget, and microclimate for efficient management of the spring resource.
- There is a need for thorough research on spring water hydrology in the context of dynamic climate and land use changes occurring in this area in order to ensure sustainable water management in the future.
- Adoption of suitable interventions, such as rainwater harvesting, surface storages/farm ponds, and water-smart technologies (drip, sprinkler, bubbler, etc.), is necessary for sustainable agriculture in different ecologies.
- Capacity building of the local communities and institutions is necessary in the safe supply and use of springwater without disturbing the ecosystem health and adoption of modern water conservation techniques.

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